

The System of Electronic Adoption of Decisions of Local Government Bodies Has Been Established

Isroilov Sharobiddin Maxammadyusufovich,

Xalilov Durbek Aminjonovich

Ferghana branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies

Annotation: According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 22, 2021 "on measures for the introduction of the electronic system "E-decision" to the activities of local government bodies" No 390 "is introduced electronic system, the development, agreement, acceptance, registration, and announcement of decisions and orders of local government bodies only through this system".

Keywords: electronic system, rule of law, activity, transparency, citizens, public, control.

The electronic system "E-decision" has been introduced to the activities of local government bodies, according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 22, 2021 "on measures for the introduction of the electronic system "E-decision" to the activities of local government bodies" No 390 ".

What is the main purpose of this system's implementation and what does it provide:

First, the rule of law and legality are guaranteed. The system examines all of the governor's decisions and includes sample decision projects from all of the interested ministries and agencies, which are conducted by various specialists. This will make the governor's choice to the developers easier and prevent incidents of legal violations. The judicial authorities also supervise all processes, from the formulation of decision-making initiatives through the governor's adoption.

Secondly, the governors' operations are encouraged to be transparent. Every decision made using the electronic system e-qaror.gov.uz on the site has a unique number that is not replicated and is automatically published, allowing all citizens, media representatives, and the general public to get acquainted with it. As a result, authorities have the ability to establish public control over the normative creative process and express a strong reaction to current law infractions.

Third, In this industry, information and communication technologies are introduced. The governors' decisions will be implemented through an electronic system, which will help to boost worker productivity. That is, decision-making, registration, and numbering are all done electronically.

Fourth, Citizens' influence and role in public control will grow. The active participation of our citizens in the process of creating local norms is ensured by the introduction of this system in all authorities of the Republic, and the authorities have created an opportunity to react to the creation of rules and norms that create conditions for violations of citizens' constitutional rights and freedoms, as well as corruption in the system.

Currently, the electronic system "e-decision" is in use "At all levels of the Republic, it has been included into the actions of local government organizations. We'll look at how effective this technique is in the legal expertization process by judicial authorities of local government decision-making projects.

The legal expertise of projects of decisions of local state authorities is established by appropriate territorial units of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to Article 27 of the law "on normative-legal acts" of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Development of the draft decision in paragraph 3 (List Number 3333, 18.11.2021) with the decree "on the development of normative-legal document projects, legal-technical formalization, legal expertization by local state authorities," Agreement, legal expertization in the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent City Departments of Justice, and the district (city) "E-decision ".

It is simply necessary to state that local government organizations are not permitted to make decisions without using the electronic system. Such documents have no legal standing and have no legal

effects as soon as they are signed. The presence of a good opinion from the territorial judicial authority following the conclusion of a legal examination is a requirement for local government authorities to make decisions.

Additionally, the draft decision will be created using an electronic system by the responsible structure subdivision of the local government authority or the territorial subdivision of the interested state authority. Through this approach, the developer submits a visa to the first leader's draft decision and sends the draft decision to the territorial units accountable for the domain of the interested state body for a severance agreement (visa issuance). The legal service will send the draft judgment to the relevant regional judicial authority for legal expertise before entering the decision-making body with the application of the legal service conclusion through the electronic system after reaching an agreement with all interested entities.

The regional judicial body receives projects of decisions from regional, district, and city councils of people's deputies via an electronic system at least five days before the councils' sessions. The first head of the regional judicial authority, or his first position, will form conclusions to the project through the computerized system based on the results of the legal expert of the draft decision.

More than 60 thousand decisions have been made by local government entities in the four months since the system's introduction.

The governors' decisions, which contradict more than 1100 legislative acts, were determined as a consequence of judicial authorities' monitoring through the electronic system of "e-decision," and suitable methods of influence on their coordination or cancellation of legislative acts were used.

The following beneficial outcomes were achieved as a result of the implementation of this system:

- 1) More than 60 thousand decisions by the governor were made electronically without the use of paper, including the reconciliation process (an average of 600 thousand papers were saved in four months);
- 2) the time it takes the governor to develop decisions and reach agreements with relevant organizations has been significantly reduced (by 25-30 percent);
- 3) The option of entering the draft resolution without going through the legal process and submitting it to the governor for signature was removed.

List Of References:

1. Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan no 390 on measures for the introduction of the electronic system "E-decree "on the activities of local state authorities" on June 22, 2021
2. <https://www.huquqiportal.uz/>
3. Khasanov Nurmukhammad. The Peculiarities of The Organization of Military-Patriotic Education in Secondary Schools. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON HUMAN COMPUTING STUDIES. Volume: 03 Issue: 2 March-April2021
4. Khasanov Nurmukhammad. Organizing and carrying out military-patriotic education in educational institutions of the republic of Uzbekistan. INTERNATIONAL ENGINEERING JOURNAL FOR RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT. Vol. 5 No. Conference (2020): ICDSIIL-20
5. <https://nrm.uz/>
6. <https://kun.uz/>
7. <https://yuz.uz/>